
pyALRA

Alexandre LANAU

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PYALRA.CORE MODULE

1.1 pyALRA.core.alra

`pyALRA.core.alra(A_norm, k=0, q=12, quantile_prob=0.001, random_state=1, svd_type=None)`

Adaptive thresholded low-rank approximation (ALRA) for imputation of sparse data.

Parameters

- **A_norm** (*ndarray or sparse matrix*) – Normalized input matrix.
- **k** (*int, optional*) – Rank for approximation; if 0, automatically chosen (default 0).
- **q** (*int, optional*) – Number of power iterations for randomized SVD (default 12).
- **quantile_prob** (*float, optional*) – Quantile threshold for adaptive thresholding (default 0.001).
- **random_state** (*int, optional*) – Random seed for reproducibility (default 1).
- **svd_type** (*str or None, optional*) – SVD method: ‘truncated’ or None for randomized SVD.

Returns

Dictionary containing: - ‘A_norm_rank_k’: low-rank approximation matrix (rank k) - ‘A_norm_rank_k_cor’: thresholded low-rank matrix - ‘A_norm_rank_k_cor_sc’: scaled and thresholded matrix (final imputed matrix)

Return type

dict

1.2 pyALRA.core.choose_k

`pyALRA.core.choose_k(A_norm, K=100, thresh=6, noise_start=80, q=12, random_state=1, svd_type=None)`

Select the rank k for low-rank approximation based on singular value gap statistics.

Parameters

- **A_norm** (*ndarray or sparse matrix*) – Normalized input matrix.
- **K** (*int, optional*) – Maximum number of singular values to consider (default 100).
- **thresh** (*float, optional*) – Threshold on number of standard deviations to detect significant singular value gap (default 6).
- **noise_start** (*int, optional*) – Index to start noise singular values (default 80).
- **q** (*int, optional*) – Number of power iterations for randomized SVD (default 12).

- **random_state** (*int, optional*) – Random seed for reproducibility (default 1).
- **svd_type** (*str or None, optional*) – SVD method: ‘truncated’ or None for randomized SVD.

Returns

Dictionary with keys: - ‘k’: selected rank - ‘num_of_sds’: array of standardized singular value differences - ‘d’: singular values array

Return type

dict

1.3 pyALRA.core.randomized_svd_py

`pyALRA.core.randomized_svd_py(A, K, q, random_state, svd_type=None)`

Perform SVD with an option for randomized or truncated SVD.

Parameters

- **A** (*ndarray or sparse matrix*) – Input data matrix to decompose.
- **K** (*int*) – Number of singular values and vectors to compute.
- **q** (*int*) – Number of power iterations (only applicable for randomized SVD).
- **random_state** (*int*) – Random seed for reproducibility.
- **svd_type** (*str or None, optional*) – If ‘truncated’, use TruncatedSVD; otherwise, use randomized SVD.

Returns

- **U** (*ndarray*) – Left singular vectors.
- **Sigma** (*ndarray*) – Singular values.
- **VT** (*ndarray*) – Right singular vectors transposed.

1.4 pyALRA.core.normalize_data

`pyALRA.core.normalize_data(A)`

Normalize data by library size and log-transform.

Parameters

A (*ndarray or sparse matrix*) – Input matrix with cells as rows and genes as columns.

Returns

Normalized and log-transformed matrix.

Return type

ndarray

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